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**Effect of copper oxide nanoparticles on regeneration and antioxidants
accumulation in vitro derived tissues of *Alhagi maurorum***

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Medicinal plants are of great interest to the researchers in the field of biotechnology as most of the drug industries. *Alhagi maurorum* is an undershrub, well known as camelthorn and always grown in salty soils and dry environment. It is widely used in folk medicines. Nanotechnology has large potential to provide an opportunity for the researchers of plant science and other fields to develop new tools for incorporation of nanoparticles into plants that could augment existing functions and add new ones. The application of nanoparticles has successfully led to the elimination of microbial contaminants from explants and demonstrated the positive role of nanoparticles in callus induction, organogenesis, somatic embryogenesis and somaclonal variation. The present investigation was focused on the effect of CuO NPs on tissue differentiation and antioxidants accumulation in cultures of *Alhagi maurorum*.

The explants (shoot tip with cotyledons, hypocotyl and roots) were cultured on MS medium with different concentrations of CuO NPs (0, 2, 4, 6, 8, 10 and 12 mg/l). MS1, MS 5 and MS6 with different conc. of CuO NPs (4, 10 and 12 mg/l) medium were best responding as compared to other tested concentrations of CuO NPs. The explants (cotyledons) show excellent growth on all MS media (MS0, MS1, MS2, MS3, MS4, MS5 and MS6) having different concentrations of CuO NPs (0, 2, 4, 6, 8, 10 and 12 mg/l) than other explants (hypocotyl and roots). The prepared CuO NPs were spherical in shape and were characterized using FTIR techniques.

Conclusion- Cu in its bulk form is vastly utilized as nutritive plant medium in callus induction and regeneration but lesser specific surface area and lower surface energy limit its reactivity. It was concluded that callogenesis and organogenesis were increased with increasing con. of CuO NPs. Now a days, there is increasing interest towards the use of herbal medicine and commercialization of plant based drugs. Thus has increased the demand as well as exploitation of *Alhagi maurorum*. Therefore, for meeting the upcoming pharmaceutical requirements, an efficient large scale propagation of this rare plant is essential.